

Report on cloud radar network survey

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1. Motivation

In the past decade, technological development has allowed **new microwave radar systems** (cloud radars, mainly at 35 and 94 GHz) to be brought to market at a **lower market cost** than in previous decades, enabling a deployment of cloud radars not seen in previous times. Today, several European sites have an operational cloud radar for cloud and precipitation studies.

However, despite lower production costs, the **technology** behind cloud radar **remains complex** and substantially **challenging to access**, especially when compared with other plug-and-play ground-based remote sensing instruments, for example, ceilometers and Doppler lidars. Optimal use of a cloud radar often requires in-depth knowledge of the instrument and the physics of scattering processes, which is usually of difficult access to operators.

For other instruments, such as microwave radiometers, one of the **most effective methods of disseminating the knowledge** necessary for properly using the instrument in all its potential has been the **creation of operator networks**. These networks aimed to share experience, practices, and methods and develop training for the operators. **MWRNET** (<http://cetemps.aquila.infn.it/mwrnet/>) is the most important example of the success of such initiatives.

Some cloud radar **networks** with different goals **already exist**, but **none include all the users** and primarily focus on putting experts in contact to share knowledge and support. Moreover, there is **not yet a centralized platform** for sharing codes, routines, and tutorials on using and visualizing data, and we still miss a standard code of conduct regarding data usage, storage, and distribution.

To overcome such difficulties and facilitate the users' work, we want to investigate the **potential benefits of starting a cloud radar support platform** to fulfill the needs mentioned above. As a preliminary step in the investigation, we prepared and distributed a survey on cloud radars to all the cloud radar users we know, as well as on the probe website and all probe social communication channels.

This survey aims to **understand the current state of the cloud radars** operating in European countries, **investigate the needs** of the operators, and **put them in contact**. The information obtained from this survey will serve as a **knowledge base** for suggesting future possible steps for the community, like proposing a cloud radar support platform for community information and sharing knowledge and tools.

2. Structure of the survey

The survey structure consists of different sections focusing on various aspects. After collecting general information on the institution that owns the instrument, specific questions focused on radar operating mode and position and the stored data formats. We then investigated the primary scientific operation purposes, goals, and unanswered needs. Then, a large section is dedicated to the current existing cloud radar networks and, finally, to the unmet needs of the users. In the following, we briefly summarize what emerged from the survey.

3. Institutions, research focus and radar settings

3.a. Institutions and manufacturers

In total, 17 institutions responded to the survey, spreading across Europe. One of them, the University of Cologne, took part twice in the survey to account for the two different sites where two radars are located (Juelich, (Germany) and Svalbard (Norway)). Most of the instruments are owned by German institutions, more than double in number compared to the other member states.

Fig 1: Distribution of cloud radar system per country (35 and 94 GHz)

Fig 2: Overview of the institutions per country that took part in the survey and own a cloud radar system

Only Italy and France, besides Germany, own more than one cloud radar, and all but three German and one French radar operate in fixed positions (see map below).

Different sites are equipped with different radar frequencies. 10 over 17 sites are equipped with only one radar frequency, and 7 instead have 2 or more operating radar systems working at different frequencies. The multifrequency option is available in one site in Romania one site in Italy, and in 6 of the 7 German sites.

Fig 3: Number of cloud radars at 35 GHz, 94 GHz in the network and number of sites equipped with both frequencies

Fig 3: Spatial location of the instruments mentioned in this document.

The Metek MIRA35 radar is the single frequency 35 GHz radar for all the sites taking part in the survey, sometimes available in scanning mode. The single frequency 94 GHz radar produced by RPG with dual polarisation mode in the model RPG-FMCW-94-DP is owned by seven institutions (Spain, Italy, Germany (3), Sweden, and Finland). In contrast, Romanian, Italian, and German institutions own the model without dual polarization (RPG-FMCW) (2). In France, the 2 94 GHz BASTA radars are produced by LATMOS and MODEM (now BOWEN). Finally, in 2 of the seven sites where two radar frequencies operate, the dual frequency radar model 35-94 GHz from RPG is deployed.

3.b. Main research foci

Cloud radar observations can contribute to multiple research areas in atmospheric sciences (see Fig. 4).

Some sites have operated their radars continuously, constructing multi-year data records that can provide **long-term monitoring** for various purposes. In particular, these long records can construct **climatologies** over different environments and be exploited in **satellite calibration/validation** actions and for **data assimilation**.

Fig 4: Main research foci of the partners of the cloud radar survey.

At the same time, the high-resolution observations of cloud and precipitation vertical profiles constitute unique datasets for investigating cloud macroscopical properties like cloud top height, cloud base, and cloud geometrical thickness over different environments in Europe. These data are crucial for **evaluating new satellite sensors like Meteosat Third Generation (MTG)** and its cloud properties retrievals in other latitudes and environmental conditions: we can observe fog, maritime clouds, and mixed-phase clouds within the whole EU, but the **possibility to use such datasets is bound to the capacity of providing them in a homogeneous data format, together with observation uncertainties**. An effort is needed to homogenize data from the different stations and characterize the uncertainty of the observed variables.

Moreover, retrieval of cloud microphysical properties can shed light on **cloud processes**, which we don't completely understand yet. The same is even more true for **precipitation processes**, where the uncertainties in retrievals from the ground and satellite demand more intense research efforts. The cloud radar community that participated in this survey can contribute by providing insights into the precipitation formation of mixed-phase and boundary layer clouds and investigating sub-cloud evaporation and sublimation of precipitation in different environments. This effort is, in particular, extremely valuable due to the difficulties in detecting boundary layer processes from satellite observations.

Additional open research questions tackle the **aerosol cloud interaction, the role of clouds in the planet's radiative budget, and clouds' radiative properties**. Finally, research from this survey's partners aims to exploit cloud radars in a network and develop synergies of instruments for various applications. Developing and empowering the cloud radar network can also allow testing algorithms and retrievals for network usage, as in the case of the fog retrieval developed at Meteo France.

3.c. Overview of currently used radar settings

3.c.i Integration time

When we look at the integration time used for the radar observations (Fig 5.), it is necessary to separate the 35 GHz from the 94 GHz because of the different working principles of the two instruments. In general, the choice of the integration time depends on the usage and the applications designed for that radar data.

Except for three sites that could not provide the integration times of their radars, we can see that for the 35 GHz, five over 7 of the radar systems use an integration time smaller than 10 seconds, and only one smaller than 3 s. When we look at 94 GHz, the number of radars working with integration times smaller than 3 s increases to 4, 3 systems keep an integration time between 3 and 5 s, and only three have it larger or equal to 10 s.

Fig 5: Integration time used for 35 GHz and for 94 GHz radar systems of the partners that took part in the cloud radar survey.

3.c.ii Doppler velocity resolution

When we look at the Doppler velocity resolution (Fig. 6) for the 35 GHz radar, typical values are 0.04 or 0.08 m/s. In comparison, for the 94 GHz radar, there's more variability also caused by the different systems. The RPG instrument scans the atmosphere in sections (chirps), and users can define settings for each chirp. For such systems, we can notice that users predominantly choose a Doppler resolution of 0.04 m/s in the chirp closest to the surface.

In contrast, for the second and third chirp, there's a tendency to pick larger and smaller resolutions, i.e., 0.06 and 0.08 and 0.02 and 0.01 m/s.

The BASTA system instead operates in different vertical modes, and the settings depend on the mode. Therefore, we cannot include that information in this analysis.

Fig 6: Doppler velocity resolution (left) and Doppler velocity range (right) adopted for 35 GHz, and for the various chirps of the 94 GHz radars.

3.c.ii Doppler velocity range

Most of the Doppler velocity range for the 35 GHz radars is around ten m/s, with only a minority of users keeping it variable (see Fig. 6). For 94 GHz radars, users pick with almost the same probability ranges, around 10 m/s, around 6 m/s, or 9 m/s for the first lowest chirp. For the second chirp, the majority picks range mainly between 7-8 m/s, and finally, for the third chirp, the Doppler range is around 4-5 m/s for all users.

3.d. Data formats, variables and data coverage

Fig 7: Temporal extension (left) and duration of the data records in years (right) for the datasets collected by the users who took part in the survey for 35 GHz and 94 GHz cloud radars.

As mentioned in the research focus section, many operators have continuously run their radars for years. The value of these observational datasets is immense for relevant applications like climatological studies and the evaluation and calibration of satellite products. Fig. 7 shows an overview of the data coverage of the 35 GHz datasets provided by the users who took part in the survey. The oldest data record dates back to 2004 and constitutes the longest record of 18 years of 35 GHz radar data. Almost half of the 35 GHz datasets are longer than ten years. The 94 GHz radar was developed more recently, and most of its data contain records that are shorter than ten years.

Regarding data formats and variables (Fig. 8), most operators store files in NCDF and level 0 (raw data) or 1 (observed variables) format. Very few operators store standard Level 2 data (products). Finally, regarding variables, people typically store the first two radar moments. They also store higher-order variables like skewness and kurtosis and the full Doppler spectra in lesser numbers. The lower number of polarimetric variables depends on the fact that not all instruments can measure polarimetric variables.

Fig 8: Data formats and variables for the data stored by the users that took part in the survey.

4. Radar networks

Fig 9: Involvement in existing radar networks for the users that took part in the survey.

88 % of the partners in the survey are already part of a radar network, with only 11.8 % not being part of any (Fig. 9). Interestingly, the most famous radar network mentioned is **ACTRIS**, with only one user telling the other **FRM4RADAR** network more recently created.

4.a. ACTRIS cloud radar network and FRM4Radar network

ACTRIS cloud radar network

Status: ACTRIS is the pan-European research infrastructure created to produce high-quality data on atmospheric constituents and it is currently running and maintaining the largest active European Cloud Radar Network within its Center for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES) (Figure 10). Currently, CCRES stores data from the MIRA Radar systems from Metek, the Radiometer Physics cloud radar binary files, and the BASTA measurement data.

For the RPG w-band radars, ACTRIS uses the processing routine from the University of Cologne, which is implemented into the general Python processing. The University of Cologne's MatLab processing code is publicly available on GitHub: <https://github.com/igmk/w-radar>. For the other data, ACTRIS uses the Level 1 data file processed by the manufacturers' routines. One of the core activities ACTRIS developed is the common data quality control throughout the retailer network.

Fig 10: Overview of the ACTRIS sites operating a cloud radar.

All these are required to make the ACTRIS cloud target classification qualitatively comparable between different sites (cloudnet.fmi.fi, <https://github.com/actris-cloudnet/cloudnetpy>). Among the activities, ACTRIS promotes radar calibration with a reference instrument, calibration monitoring using disdrometers acting as independent sensors, or based on Cloudsat and, in the future, EarthCARE Cloud precipitation radar (CPR).

Plans: As planned future activities, ACTRIS envisions the monitoring of the antenna off-zenith pointing. Moreover, it demands all development to be open source and usable individually if needed. In addition, CCRES will go on developing and requesting operation procedures for cloud observations to best perform their target classification or Satellite CPR calibration and validation. Nevertheless, the development of standard radar processing, including all sensors and data formats, is still open. A standard cloud radar Doppler spectra data format might also be worth developing for further applications. Furthermore, documentation for the existing radar systems and the next generations can always be improved. Another helpful point would be developing a centralized web page to collect information for radar beginners and document best practices for more experienced users.

FRM4Radar network

ESA initiated the FRM4Radar network to foster the development of radar data quality control and satellite radar cal/val methods. Because cloud radars in space use w-band, the network insists on four w-band radars from RPG. The project contributed to improving the existing Matlab data processing from the University of Cologne. A reflectivity monitoring tool was also developed and tested, and the experience gained was transferred to the development of the ACTRIS monitoring toolkit. The development of the antenna off-zenith pointing monitoring also started within this project. Finally, a Satellite Radar forward simulation tool, `orbital-radar.py`, was developed for the project (www.github.com/igmk/orbital-radar). The project also produced material about radar operation and suggested best practices for satellite cal/val usage of ground-based radars. It thus represents a good example of how small initiatives can interact with more extensive networks and benefit from each other developments.

4.b. Benefits

We then investigated what are the main benefits that ACTRIS provides to its partners, and we could group the answers into three macro-areas that are summarized in Fig 11:

Fig 11: Benefits of being part of ACTRIS network based on the replies of users who took part in the survey.

- **Benefits as a community member:** ACTRIS grants involvement in EU projects and calibration campaigns for satellite sensors that are hardly accessible otherwise. It allows the exchange of experience in installing and operating the instruments. It makes disseminating and sharing data to a broader community easier than a single user can achieve alone.
- **Benefits concerning data processing:** ACTRIS offers centralized, homogeneous, and real-time data processing with standardized procedures and products. It also provides methods that are quality checked and grant given quality standards, and finally, it allows high-level synergistic product development.
- **Benefits concerning instrument maintenance:** Within ACTRIS, it is possible to access funding for instrument maintenance, and it is easier to receive instrument monitoring and operational support, for example, in practices like calibration.

4.c. Unanswered needs

Despite the great positive feedback obtained on ACTRIS by the radar users that took part in the survey, we also opted to investigate if, from the users' perspective, there is something more or better that networks can do. We started by asking if there was any need they perceived as unanswered by the networks they were part of.

Surprisingly, here, **58.8% of the people have some needs that still should be fulfilled by the networks they are part of**, which, based on the previous answers, is mainly ACTRIS. 41.2% of them who do not have unanswered needs (Fig 12).

With the scope of obtaining suggestions for the community's future development in and outside ACTRIS, we asked to specify what types of needs are more urgent. Based on the answers, we identified the specific areas depicted in Fig. 13:

Do you have unanswered needs?

Fig 12: Involvement in existing radar networks for the users that took part in the survey.

Fig 13: Map of unanswered needs suggested from the users taking part to the cloud radar network survey

Various users highlighted some knowledge gaps they would love to fix. There is a growing interest in **performing scanning operation** modes and consequential complex data analysis, but little knowledge on the topic is present in the network. People also need training on performing **attenuation correction to precipitation fields** and properly exploiting the 89 GHz channel attached to many of the RPG 94 GHz radar systems. Additional efforts should also spread knowledge on **different calibration procedure** techniques, such as those involving disdrometers.

Another critical aspect concerns the availability of documentation on data processing and instrument operation. Many users **demand detailed documentation** on the whole data processing chain that can convert raw into level 2 data. Some codes for data processing, for example, the conversion from L0 to L2 files by LATMOS, are proprietary, hindering the possibility of understanding how to manipulate data fully. Also, re-processing the radar data from raw to L0 format can be challenging because conversion is followed by an irreversible data transfer, which makes the raw data not accessible anymore. They thus ask for **open-source processing scripts**. Also, only RPG radar manuals contain the documentation on operating the radars, and people found it incomplete, proposing improvements and extensions. There is also a strong demand for more **user-friendly processing descriptions** and a request to be faster in fixing software bugs to one of the leading manufacturers, the RPG company.

Finally, people highlighted the difficulty of accessing all aspects of cloud radar physics, from maintenance to processing and data analysis. In particular, they stressed the absence of **easily accessible hands-on tutorials**, processing scripts, and documentation in a centralized location.

This **lack of open-access resources** on the different aspects of knowledge needed to run and maintain a radar system makes it difficult for people in the network to operate radar instruments properly, and it is crucial to facilitate access to the field to new and early career scientists.

5. Potential for new support platform

Moved by the feedback on the unanswered needs, we investigated what could have been the users' attitude towards a potential radar support network or a new platform. Inspired by the Pytroll platform, developed for the satellite community, we aimed to retrieve elements of reflection on the usefulness of a similar tool for the cloud radar community.

70.6% of the interviewed users replied positively to the possibility of a new support platform for radar users, while the remaining **29.4% were more unsure** (see Fig 14)

Fig 14: Interest in joining a new cloud radar support platform expressed by the participants of the survey.

5.a. Expected benefits

We thus investigated which expectations existed concerning such a platform, and specifically what people were aiming at in terms of support tools.

We could group the received answers in three main areas, that are shown in Fig. 15.

Fig 15: Expected benefits of a new radar support platform detailed by the participants of the survey.

It is relevant to consider that all the mentioned areas deal with the **core need to collaborate and share knowledge** and relate to the fact that the best scientific results and publication can be obtained when people work together.

People wished to **share updated knowledge and best practices** for instrument deployment in challenging environments. Moreover, they hope that we could, as a community, achieve a better **sharing of the algorithms and tools for data analysis, visualization, processing, and quality control**. One of the best comments we received, which we love to report here, motivated this effort as *"not to reinvent the wheel again"*.

A more powerful support platform is envisaged to **discuss common issues and share API and software modules**. People also suggested **empowering** the existing **CCRES** network and using the platform to increase users' skills and make them able to adapt to the growing needs of the cloud radar network. Finally, they also suggested that such a platform could be a perfect entry-level for scientists starting to work with radars from scratch.

Finally, many proposed using such a platform to put together new ideas, **develop joint publications**, and **find agreement on standard operating procedures**.

The platform could also facilitate the enhancement of existing software and make it easier to apply algorithms to new sites or develop entirely new retrievals.

Figure 16 summarizes the expected types of support that the users who took part in the survey expect from such a platform. In agreement with the written comments provided above, most interest is in product development and maintenance practices.

Fig 16: Summarized types of support for the envisaged platform.

Fig 17: Percentage of people interested in being involved in a support platform.

Finally, 94.1% (Fig. 17) of them would love to be involved and informed if any institution will proceed in the direction of setting up such a platform and people were happy to provide the suggestions we report below:

Suggestions from the users

"How the pytroll like tool that you are considering will be related to py-Art and cloudnetpy?"

"Very good idea to set up a cloud radar support platform!"

"Great initiative, Go ahead. In the future a common calibration strategy will be beneficial."

"Do not create a new network, just extending CLOUDNET goals"

"In the past, several attempts to establish such radar support networks have been unsuccessful. It takes a lot of effort to fill such a network with life and content and the co-operation of the participating Radar PIs. I would therefore argue in favour of using and supporting CCRES within the framework of ACTRIS. As far as I know, (almost?) all European radar operators are members of ACTRIS."

6. Recommendations

The answers and suggestions collected from this survey are like dots of a hidden image, and our task as proposers of the investigation is to connect them.

The survey highlighted that, at the moment, cloud radar users across the EU have some **needs** that are **unanswered** by the existing networks (ACTRIS, FM4RADARS). They ask for **complete documentation on data processing and operating the instrument**. They also demand **open access** and easily accessible **processing codes** and call for creating **platforms** where newbies can, with less difficulty, access **learning material on radars** and get **tutorials** and hands-on to get started. They also perceive the need to strengthen the network to **do more science together**: they mention the desire to run algorithms developed on one site in another location of the network, write publications together, and exchange ideas.

The network is mature enough to **adopt a cooperative approach at a European level** and discard former competitive attitudes within EU institutions and countries. This aspect will be **crucial to gaining new scientific developments** and sharing knowledge, as the people in the network ask. These are times in which there is an enormous potential for scientific development. New research is expanding on developing new radar instruments operating at **new frequencies and advanced radar-scanning strategies** to monitor cloud evolution from the ground. By exploiting AI methods, **big data can provide new input for analyzing cloud radar Doppler spectra** and other high-resolution radar datasets. People are also eager to investigate the best employment of the available channels and frequencies of the new radar systems and **demand the diffusion of knowledge on complex retrieval approaches** (for example, calculation of precipitation attenuation) developed only in some network institutions. Moreover, many sites are now equipped with dual frequencies, but the knowledge of dual frequency retrievals and future developments still need to be improved across the network.

Finally, we agree with the users that there's **no need for another cloud radar support network**. We **bring this recommendation to the ACTRIS infrastructure, particularly CCRES**, the most popular and well-known among our users.

We ask ACTRIS to receive suggestions from the user emerging in this document **and implement changes to fulfill their requests**. A support platform of the type we initially imagined (a tool like the Pytroll created for the satellite community or the Py-Art created for weather and cloud radars by the ARM community) is necessary to satisfy the requests that the users highlighted. **We envision a platform** that can store and make available online:

- Codes and processing routines
- Documentation and manuals
- Information on the instrument producers
- Links to quicklooks of the observations from the different sites
- Maps with operating radars

- Reports of measurement campaigns and good practices
- Publications grouped by topics for relevant studies on cloud radars
- List of existing cloud radar networks
- Description of data formats and best practices for archiving data
- Link to a communication platform and help support community (Slack channel or similar)
- Periodic meetings of the community on hot topics
- List of stakeholders of radar products (satellite, airports, meteorological services)
- Rules of conduct for code and material distribution
- Link to dataset download and data policy

Such a platform will fulfill the survey's sharing, collaboration, and research development expectations. It will also constitute a valuable tool for new scientists accessing radar science.

Finally, we also think that it would be absolutely beneficial if CCRES will organize, as a follow up of the survey, a **cloud radar workshop for a broader community including international guests**, to discuss and expand on the solutions to the topics raised by the

7. Conclusions

This report presented the survey results prepared by the PROBE COST Action for cloud radar users. The survey aimed to investigate the status of the European cloud radar network and the operators' needs.

We wanted to understand in which areas of our cooperation among different radar community members we still had some room for improvement, and we also aimed to identify possible future meaningful directions of development.

We thus asked questions covering different aspects, from general operating settings of radars to research interests and focus, involvement in radar networks, and unanswered needs and expectations as radar users part of some networks.

We then analyzed and organized the responses to get clear messages and information on the current status and needs. We also formulated a constructive proposal for activities and tools to implement in the future to improve the situation and promote cooperation among European partners.

We want to thank everyone who participated in the survey and shared their experiences and thoughts. They were all precious contributions; we hope to have made the best of them.

